

NUMERICAL STUDY OF STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING OF WING BOX STRUCTURES USING EMBEDDED FIBER BRAGG GRATING SENSORS

T. Okabe and H. Sekine

*Department of Aerospace Engineering, Tohoku University
6-6-01 Aoba-yama, Aoba-ku, Sendai 980-8579, Japan*

SUMMARY: We proposed a new method to identify the shape of the interfacial damage between the hat shape stringer and the skin panel of wing box structures using embedded fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors. Our proposed method assumed that these sensors were embedded into the interface between the hat shape stringer and the skin panel of wing box structures. We analyzed two types of data (average strain and reflected spectrum), which are detected by the embedded FBG sensors, to identify the shape of the interfacial damage. We demonstrated numerical examples to validate our proposed method. The identification results are in good agreements with the exact results. Our proposed method using embedded FBG sensors is effective in identifying interfacial damage between the hat shaped stringer and the skin panel of wing box structures.

KEYWORDS: Damage identification, Wing box structure, Hat shape stringer, Skin panel, FEA, Structural health monitoring, FBG sensor, Optical analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The engineering application of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) composites in the aircraft structures requires the establishment of health monitoring technology during the service period [1]. This study proposes a new method to identify the shape of the interfacial damage between the hat shape stringer and the skin panel of wing box structures using embedded fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors. The FBG sensor is a type of optical fiber sensor that is sensitive to both average strain and strain distribution in the gauge section. Moreover, FBG sensors can easily be multiplied in a single optical fiber [2-6]. Our proposed method utilizes the unique ability of FBG sensors to identify the shape of the interfacial damage. Based on the information detected by the FBG sensors, using the optimization technique, this method can identify the shape of the interfacial damage. The validity of our method is discussed by comparing the identified values with the exact results.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Figure 1 schematically represents the analyzed model. We calculated the stress and strain fields of the model using a 3D finite element method. The calculation procedure of the finite element analysis (FEA) is briefly presented below.

Fig.1: Schematic of stiffened panel

Our model must first properly address the contact state within the interfacial damage area. We avoided an inadmissible overlap in the contact region with the penalty function method. The modified potential energy Π of the model is then given by

$$\Pi = \Pi_p + H_p \quad (1)$$

$$\Pi_p = \frac{1}{2} \int_v \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} \mathbf{U} dv - \int_s \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{F} ds \quad (2)$$

$$H_p = \frac{1}{2} \int_{s_i} \tilde{\mathbf{U}}^T \tilde{\mathbf{N}}^T \alpha \tilde{\mathbf{N}} \tilde{\mathbf{U}} ds \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{U} is the nodal displacement vector of the model, $\tilde{\mathbf{U}}$ is the nodal displacement vector of the interfacial damage area, \mathbf{B} is the strain-displacement transformation matrix, \mathbf{D} is the constitution matrix, \mathbf{F} is the external force vector, $\tilde{\mathbf{N}}$ is the relative displacement–nodal displacement matrix for the interfacial damage area and α is the penalty number. In Eqn. 3, s_i denotes the interfacial damage area. Therefore, the basic equation of the deformation for our model is given by

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial \mathbf{U}} = \mathbf{0} \quad (4)$$

The contact state within the interfacial damage area is iteratively checked after calculating Eqn. 4, and the penalty function term H_p is recalculated. Figure 2 presents the typical mesh of the FEA. This model consists of 8,575 nodes and 1,990 elements. We analyzed it using the isoparametric 15- node solid elements, assuming that both the hat shape stringer and the skin panel consist of quasi-isotropic composite laminates. Table 1 lists the material properties of this analysis. We applied compressive loads on the edge of the skin panel, using the boundary conditions given by Raju et al [7]. We addressed the interfacial damage on the edge of the stringer (Fig. 2) and assumed that an ellipse could approximate the shape of the interfacial damage. This elliptical shape must be arbitrary during the damage identification process based on the optimization technique mentioned later. We adjusted the finite element mesh to the changing shapes of the damaged area, utilizing the automatic mesh generator (Delaunay triangulation approach [8]).

MESH GENERATION

We automatically generated the mesh to represent the shape of the interfacial damage. First, we generated the two-dimensional mesh using the Delaunay triangulation approach, as shown in Fig. 2 (a) [8]. However, the mesh generated only by the Delaunay triangulation approach is

generally warped. Therefore, the post processing is required to obtain the fine mesh. We utilized the index given as

$$DTR = \{(l_1^2 - l_2^2)^2 + (l_2^2 - l_3^2)^2 + (l_3^2 - l_1^2)^2\} / (4S^2) \quad (5)$$

where l_1, l_2 and l_3 are the length of the side of the three-node element and S is the area of that element. This index indicates the state how the shape of the element is close to a regular triangle. If the DTR of the corresponding element is zero, it is just a regular triangle. We minimized the DTR value by moving the nodes. Second, we expanded the two-dimensional mesh into the three-dimensional mesh, as shown in Fig. 2(b).

OPTICAL ANALYSIS

We calculated the reflected spectrum of FBG sensors using the transfer matrix approach, by inputting the strain distribution from the FEA. We assumed that the gauge sections L could be divided into NL nodes as shown in Fig. 3. The complex spectra of the forward and backward waves, A and B , for the $i-1^{\text{th}}$ and i^{th} nodes must satisfy the following equations [9]:

Table 1: Material properties

$E_{11} = 66.49[\text{GPa}]$	$E_{22} = 66.49[\text{GPa}]$	$E_{33} = 9.57[\text{GPa}]$
$G_{12} = 66.49[\text{GPa}]$	$G_{23} = 3.50[\text{GPa}]$	$G_{31} = 3.50[\text{GPa}]$
$\nu_{12} = 0.26$	$\nu_{23} = 0.49$	$\nu_{13} = 0.49$

Fig. 2: Finite element mesh

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_i \\ B_i \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{F}_i \begin{bmatrix} A_{i-1} \\ B_{i-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\mathbf{F}_i = \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ \bar{b} & \bar{a} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$a = \exp(i\phi l) \left(\frac{e^{\alpha l} + e^{-\alpha l}}{2} - i \frac{\varphi}{\alpha} \frac{e^{\alpha l} - e^{-\alpha l}}{2} \right), \quad b = -i \frac{\kappa}{\alpha} \exp(i\phi l) \frac{e^{\alpha l} - e^{-\alpha l}}{2} \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha = \sqrt{\kappa^2 - \varphi^2}, \quad \kappa = \frac{\pi}{\lambda} \delta n, \quad \varphi = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} n_{eff} - \frac{\pi}{\Lambda} \quad (9)$$

Note that κ is the mode-coupling coefficient, φ is the detuning parameter that represents the phase matching condition, λ is the wavelength of interest, n_{eff} is the effective refractive index of the core, δn is the depth of the refractive index, Λ is the grating period, and \bar{a} and \bar{b} are the conjugates of a and b . In particular, Λ and n_{eff} are functions of longitudinal strain ε_f applied to the FBG sensor, and are given by

$$\Lambda = (1 + \varepsilon_f) \Lambda_0 \quad (10)$$

$$n_{eff} = n_0 - \frac{n_0^3}{2} \{ p_{12} - \nu_f (p_{11} + p_{12}) \} \varepsilon_f \quad (11)$$

where Λ_0 is the initial period of the index modulation, ν_f is Poisson's ratio of the optical fiber, and p_{11} and p_{12} are the strain-optic coefficients where subscripts 1 and 2 denote the axial and transverse directions of the optical fiber. Then, A and B for $i=0$ and $i=NL$ are then given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_{NL} \\ B_{NL} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{F} \begin{bmatrix} A_0 \\ B_0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_{NL} \mathbf{F}_{NL-1} \dots \mathbf{F}_1 \quad (13)$$

Equation 12 is thus the basic matrix equation for determining the reflected spectrum. The boundary conditions are

$$A_0 = 1, B_{NL} = 0 \quad (14)$$

After solving Eqn. 12 subject to the boundary conditions, we calculated the intensity of the reflected spectrum R as a function of wavelength λ by

$$R(\lambda) = |B_0|^2 \quad (15)$$

Table 2 lists the parameters of the optical fiber and the FBG sensor used in this analysis.

IDENTIFICATION METHOD

As mentioned above, the FBG sensor is sensitive to both average strain and strain distribution in the gauge section. This study addressed sensors embedded into the interface

Fig.3: Schematic of gauge section in the FBG sensor

between the hat shape stringer and the skin panel of wing box structures, as shown in Fig. 4. To identify the shape of the interfacial damage, we utilized both types of data detected by the embedded FBG sensors.

First, we identified the shape of the interfacial damage using the average strain for each gauge section as shown in Fig. 5. We then set the minor and major axes (p, q) of the elliptical crack as design variables and identified their values by solving the following optimization problem:

$$\text{Minimize: } F = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\varepsilon_i - \varepsilon_i^M)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (\varepsilon_i^M)^2} \quad (16)$$

Design variables: p, q

Table2: Parameters of optical fiber and FBG sensor

$\lambda_0 = 1550$ [nm]	$n_0 = 1.449$
$p_{11} = 0.113$	$p_{12} = 0.252$

Fig.4: Schematic of embedded FBG sensors between hat shape stringer and skin panel

Fig.5: Schematic of gauge sections in embedded FBG sensors

Here, N is the number of gauge sections, ε_i is the calculated average strain of the i th gauge section obtained from the FEA and ε_i^M is the measured average strain of the i^{th} gauge section obtained from the peak shift of the reflected spectrum.

Second, we used the shape of the reflected spectrum of each FBG sensor, influenced by the strain distribution of the gauge section, to identify the shape of the interfacial damage. Next, we identified the minor and major axes (p, q) of the elliptical crack by solving the following optimization problem:

$$\text{Minimize: } F = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^M (a_m - a_m^M)^2}{\sum_{m=1}^M (a_m^M)^2} \quad (17)$$

Design variables: p, q

We represented the reflected spectrum by a Fourier series to evaluate the shape of the reflected spectrum as shown in Fig. 6. In Eqn. 17, a_m and a_m^M are the m -th Fourier coefficients for the calculated and measured spectra, and for this study we adopted $M=300$.

The objective functions in Eqns. 16 and 17 possess many local optima in the design space. Therefore, the simple optimization for either Eqn. 16 or 17 cannot identify the shape of the interfacial damage accurately. Our proposed method identified the minor and major axes (p, q) of the elliptical crack as follows:

Step 1: Generate the initial values with the random number generator. Here, the average strain of each gauge section with those initial values, calculated by FEM, must satisfy the following inequality.

$$\frac{(\varepsilon_i - \varepsilon_i^M)^2}{(\varepsilon_i^M)^2} < e \quad (i=1, \dots, N) \quad (18)$$

where e is a threshold value. If the initial value does not satisfy Eqn. 18, we must reject the initial value.

Step 2: Solve Eqn. 16 using the optimization technique (Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (BFGS) variable metric method with polynomial interpolation after finding the bounds) with the initial values obtained in the previous step.

Fig.6: Calculated spectrum configuration

Step 3: Solve Eqn. 17 using the optimization technique with the identified values in Step 2 as initial values.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES OF DAMAGE IDENTIFICATION

This study addressed numerical examples as listed in Tables 3 and 4. We adopted $N=4, 9$ as two cases of the number of gauge sections for the identification. We set two exact values for design variables in each identification case. Moreover, we set the measured values of ε_i^M and a_m^M in Eqns. 16 and 17 which are calculated by the direct FEA plus the optical analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tables 3 and 4 show the identification results. We established the threshold value as $e=0.25$ in Step 1. In this identification, we identified the shape of the interfacial damage from Step 2 through Step 3 again after we once did it from Step 1 through Step 3. We prepared for two pairs of initial values, which satisfy the condition (i.e. Eqn. 18) yielded in Step 1. While all of the identification results with $N=9$ are in good agreements with the exact results, the identification results with $N=4$ depend on the initial values. Therefore, if FBG sensors with the sufficient number of gauge sections are embedded into the interfaces, our proposed method is effective to identify the shape of the interfacial damage between the hat shape stringer and the skin panel of wing box structures.

Our study assumed that we could approximate the shape of the interfacial damage as an ellipse. In practice, it would be more desirable to address the arbitrary shape of a damaged area. We did not consider the loss of intensity due to local bending of the optical fiber. We will address these issues in the near future.

Table3:Identification results (N=4)

	Exact results		Initial values		Identification results	
	p	q	p	q	p	q
Case1	17.30 * 15.39		17.21 * 17.64		17.66 * 15.01	
			19.01 * 15.88		17.83 * 14.10	
Case2	12.41 * 6.80		15.19 * 6.35		15.48 * 6.81	
			13.21 * 10.44		12.75 * 6.79 [mm]	

Table4:Identification results (N=9)

	Exact results		Initial values		Identification results	
	p	q	p	q	p	q
Case1	17.30 * 15.39		18.35 * 15.25		17.32 * 15.31	
			18.27 * 14.81		17.61 * 15.41	
Case2	12.41 * 6.80		12.14 * 6.53		12.27 * 6.73	
			15.55 * 6.84		12.29 * 6.62 [mm]	

CONCLUSIONS

We proposed a new method using embedded FBG sensors to identify the shape of the interfacial damage between the hat shaped stringer and the skin panel of wing box structures. Our proposed method utilized two types of data (average strain and reflected spectrum) detected by embedded FBG sensors. Using the transfer matrix approach, we calculated the reflected spectra of FBG sensors by inputting the strain distribution calculated by the FEA in which the penalty function method avoided an inadmissible overlap in the contact region. The identification results ($N=9$) are in good agreement with the exact results. We found that the proposed method using embedded FBG sensors was effective in identifying the shape of the interfacial damage between the hat shaped stringer and the skin panel of wing box structures.

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